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FDA action against compounders

Issue/Problem

On [February 6](#), the FDA announced it was taking action against ‘copycat’ drugs, restricting the use of active ingredients in compounded versions of semaglutide weight-loss drugs. The announcement responded to news from Hims & Hers that it would offer a compounded version of Novo Nordisk’s drug, Wegovy, at a lower price. On February 9, Novo Nordisk [filed a patent infringement lawsuit](#) against Hims & Hers.

Description of the Problem

Two exceptions to patent rights exists for compounded drugs: (i) when a patient requires a specialized treatment, or (ii) when a medication is on the [Drug Shortages list](#). Semaglutide medications [were listed](#) on that list from March 2022 to February 2025.

The increased regulatory scrutiny of generic compounded semaglutide drugs comes amid the Trump administration’s attempts to balance the goals of improving [drug affordability](#) and encouraging investment from pharmaceutical companies, including [tariff exemptions](#) provided to pharmaceutical companies that invest in the US market.

Results

While Novo Nordisk’s patent infringement case is still pending, the FDA’s approach would effectively reinforce Novo Nordisk’s market exclusivity while placing telehealth providers under greater regulatory scrutiny. By restricting the compounding of semaglutide once removed from the Drug Shortages list, the FDA narrowed one of the only viable low-cost alternatives available outside the formal approval pathway.

Lessons Learned

The episode illustrates how FDA enforcement decisions can materially influence pharmaceutical market dynamics independently of statutory patent expansion, and how the Trump administration continues to build partnerships with established pharma companies. The FDA’s actions follow [the company’s commitment](#) to invest \$10B in the US market and offer lower-cost access to its semaglutide medications through the TrumpRX platform.